

"inversion" of ternary equilibrium system and Earth's magnetic field

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Summary: geomagnetic inversion refers to the alternating phenomenon of the earth magnetic pole in the geological period. geomagnetism inversion, also called geomagnetic reversal. It refers to the 180 change in the direction of the earth's magnetic field, or the polarity of the geomagnetic poles. The results of paleogeomagnetic research confirm that the polarity of the Earth's magnetic field has been reversed many times.

Key words: ternary balance system; magnetic pole inversion; magnetic pole flip; Earth's magnetic field; magnetic field offset

Introduction

The inversion of the geomagnetic field was initially found in residual magnetic measurements of the rock. In explaining this phenomenon, it was proposed that rock magnetization is directed opposite to the direction of modern geomagnetic field, possibly due to the rock formation direction opposite to the direction of modern geomagnetic field. For this view could not be affirmed at the time. So, it was once called the geomagnetic field inversion hypothesis.

1. Earth's magnetic pole movement

1.1 Current status of Earth magnetic pole research

In recent years, according to the ancient geomagnetic research, not only confirmed that the polarity of the geomagnetic poles has indeed undergone many inversion. Moreover, according to the hypothesis of electromagnetic hydrodynamics and other geophysical processes, it is possible to prove that the geomagnetic field inversion phenomenon is completely possible. Astronomical observations have also found periodic polar inversion of many stars. The discovery and confirmation of the phenomenon of geomagnetic field inversion is very important to explore the cause of the Earth's magnetic field.

1.2 Relevant theories derived from the ternary equilibrium law

The above contents are some studies by scientists on the inversion of the Earth's magnetic field. However, according to the conclusion of the law of ternary balance, the celestial body produces the corresponding magnetic field relative to the absolute stationary space movement, and the earth's rotation of the earth is this kind of spatial movement relative to the absolute static, so it will inevitably produce a magnetic field perpendicular to the direction of motion.

Through this theoretical analysis, it is roughly concluded that the reversal of the earth's magnetic field generated from rotation is absolutely impossible. But why do some scientists find that the direction of rock magnetization is the opposite direction of the modern magnetic field?

In fact, this phenomenon is not formed after the reversal of the earth's magnetic pole, but after the earth's magnetic pole offset. Why is the earth's magnetic pole offset caused by it? Is there any theoretical basis?

1.3 Earth Movement Superposition and Earth Magnetic Pole Offset

Its fundamental theory is that "the movement of objects relative to the absolute static space, will inevitably produce a movement direction vertical magnetic field state", that is to say, the rotation of the earth, will actually be with the movement of the earth in the cosmic space, the superposition of movement state, different movement state will lead to the earth magnetic pole of different degrees of deflection phenomenon.

The link line between the earth's north-south magnetic pole, here we temporarily call it the "north-south pole axis", "north-south pole axis" will always be perpendicular to the superposition direction of "the earth's rotation movement and the overall movement of the earth's motion in the cosmic space".

That is to say, if the rotation of the earth is regarded as the circular movement of the object around the central point, then add a movement perpendicular to the rotation direction, the superposition direction of "the earth's rotation of the direction and the overall movement of the earth in the cosmic space" will form a spiral upward movement state. The "north-south magnetic pole axis" will always be perpendicular to "the direction of the earth's rotation movement and the superposition direction of the overall movement of the earth in the cosmic space", that is, "perpendicular to the center of the plane formed by the spiral curve", reflected in the state of the actual magnetic field of the earth that is "the direction of the earth's north-south magnetic pole will also rotate with the earth's rotation".

1.4 Schematic diagram of Earth motion superposition and Earth magnetic pole offset

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Schematic diagram of the resulting pole deflection changes after the Earth relative to absolute stationary space rotation superimposed with other speeds. The magnetic field eventually presented by the earth is mainly affected by the earth's rotation of the earth and the superposition of the earth's absolute movement in the universe, so when the time the earth's magnetic pole is closer to the geographical north-south pole, the earth's overall magnetic field will be relatively weakened. This weakening of the Earth's magnetic field is not a "precursor to the inversion of the Earth's magnetic pole" predicted by ordinary scientists, but the gradual parallel of the absolute direction of the earth to the Earth's rotation plane (equatorial plane).

2. Superposition of Earth rotation and overall movement

2.1 Earth motion superposition to form a magnetic polar offset

The position of the Earth at the equator, the size of the motion velocity generated by the Earth's rotation, is about 0.465km/s, so the overall velocity generated by the Earth's rotation, should be about 0.147km/s.

We assume that if the Earth is in the universe, there is still a motion relative to other directions of the absolute rest space in a direction perpendicular to the Earth's rotation. When the magnitude of this velocity of motion is equal to the overall velocity produced by the Earth's rotation, or about 0.147km/s, it causes about 45 deflection of the Earth's magnetic field. If this speed reaches about 0.3km/s, the Earth's magnetic defts about 60.

The Earth revolves around the solar system within the solar system, and the solar system revolves around the center of the Milky Way. However, between the galaxy and other galaxies, there is the complex influence of the magnetic field force generated

by gravity and motion, so the overall moving state of the galaxy is a relatively complex state of motion. This "Earth still has an other motion in the universe relative to absolute stationary space" is the superposition state of this complex motion.

2.2 The relation between overall superposition of Earth and magnetic pole

This speed of the Earth in cosmic space relative to the absolute stationary space, when parallel to the rotation direction of the Earth, the magnetic pole coincides with the geographical north-south pole of the Earth. When the direction of the Earth's rotation is not parallel to the Earth's motion relative to the absolutely stationary cosmic space, the Earth's magnetic polar inconsistency occurs (including other secondary factors. For example, lava movement in the crust, ocean currents, etc.).

Theoretically, the maximum value of this magnetic pole deflection can be infinitely close to 90. That is, the position of the earth's magnetic pole, which can even appear anywhere near the equator, but it is absolutely impossible to show a true reversal (north-south pole alignment). (Unless extremely low probability of object impact events occur, as on Mars, causing changes in the direction of rotation of Earth.)

3. Conclusion

Due to the specific location of the earth's magnetic pole, it will be affected by the change of the earth's overall movement in the cosmic space, and a gradual change of the earth's magnetic pole position appears. So over time, the direction of rock magnetization at the same location appears, showing different states at different periods. The magnetic field generated by the solar rotation will also be similar. The magnetic polar deflection of the sun will also have some impact on the overall operation of the solar system.

Literature:

[1] 《三元平衡定律》: <https://zenodo.org/record/4989581#.YNLOJKgzZPb> (June 8, 2021)

The English version is converted by translation software, so there may be many translation errors.